

Synthesis of CdS Nanoparticles: Surface Morphology and Optical Study

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Abstract

In the present study, high-quality cadmium sulfide (CdS) nanoparticles were synthesized using a simple and low-cost chemical precipitation method. Particle size control was achieved through the use of thioglycerol as a capping agent. The optical properties of the synthesized CdS nanoparticles were investigated using UV–visible spectroscopy, which revealed strong absorption in the visible region with a noticeable blue shift of the absorption edge toward shorter wavelengths, confirming the nanoscale nature of the CdS particles. To explore their applicability in optoelectronic devices, CdS nanoparticle thin films were fabricated using the spin-coating technique. The surface morphology of the deposited films was examined using field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM), which confirmed the formation and uniform distribution of nanoparticles. The results demonstrate that the chemical precipitation approach provides an effective and scalable route for producing CdS nanoparticles suitable for low-cost optoelectronic applications, including solar cells and light-emitting diodes.

Keywords: CdS, nanoparticles, chemical precipitation, FE-SEM, UV-visible spectroscopy.

1. Introduction

Chalcogenide based materials are of vitally important for the sustainable development of modern society. Their roles in advanced equipment in green energy harvesting, defense technology, space technology, and biomedical industries are unparalleled [1-3]. These chalcogenide based II-VI semiconductors are versatile materials in terms of physical and chemical properties. They possesses an excellent optoelectronic properties that made them a special among other materials. Among the chalcogenide compounds, CdS is the simplest one to synthesis because of its favorable chemical properties. The CdS has the direct bandgap energy of 2.4 to 2.5 eV. The synthesis of CdS nanoparticles provides an opportunity to tailor the optical, electronic and surface properties because of quantum confinement effect [4-6]. The importance of CdS nanoparticles is to achieve precise bandgap and emission wavelength through via controlling the growth of particle size. This peculiar characteristics is applicable to fabricate high-performance optoelectronic devices, particularly, in quantum dot solar cells, the band alinement with interface layer has significantly enhanced charge separation and reduced non-radiative recombination. Nanoparticles of CdS also played a crucial role in making of high color purity light-emitting diode. Besides, it is also used in photocatalytic reactions such as organic pollutant degradation and hydrogen gas evolution.

There are several ways to synthesize the CdS nanoparticles, particularly, solvothermal method, hydrothermal method, sol-gel technique, sonochemical method, combustion, micro-emulsion, wet-chemical synthesis, chemical reduction synthesis and thermal decomposition techniques etc [4-13]. Among the various preparation strategies, low-temperature chemical precipitation synthesis methods is particularly important as it enable cost-effective, scalable, and substrate-compatible formation of CdS nanoparticles while keeping its intrinsic physical properties. The chemical precipitation method allow the formation of CdS nanoparticles at temperatures below 100 °C, offering precise control over particle size, morphology, and surface states through adjustment of precursor concentration, pH, and reaction kinetics. Although nanoparticles synthesized at low temperatures may exhibit high defect densities compared to those prepared under hydrothermal conditions, controlled synthesis and post-treatment strategies can effectively tailor surface states to enhance charge separation, photoluminescence efficiency, and visible-light activity [4]. Moreover, low-temperature synthesis facilitates integration of CdS nanoparticles onto

flexible substrates and layered device architectures, making it particularly attractive for next-generation photovoltaic, optoelectronic, and photocatalytic applications. Beyond optoelectronics, the synthesis of CdS nanoparticles is crucial for photocatalytic applications, where surface-related phenomena dominate performance. And for this purpose, surface passivation, dopant incorporation and heterostructure formation processes are adopted to enhance photo-stability, catalytic efficiency. Therefore, this method is more robust and has a great potential to achieve large scale production in order to incorporate into vast green energy production system.

In the present study, we have explored the synthesis of CdS nanoparticles by chemical precipitation method to study the surface morphology and optical properties of the synthesized materials.

Experimental Details

All the chemicals were of A. R. grade and purchased from LOBA Chem Pvt. Ltd. They were used without any further purification. Cadmium nitrates $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and thiourea ($\text{CH}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}$) were used as precursors for Cd and S ions. Thioglycerol was used to control the size of CdS nanoparticles. The cadmium and sulphur precursors were added into round bottom flask. The thioglycerol was added in an appropriate amount to control the size of CdS nanoparticles. The pH and reaction temperature were controlled. After the completion of reaction, the precipitate was collected and washed with ethanol and deionized water several times to remove residual ions and impurities. Finally, the synthesized nanoparticles of CdS are dried in air at 100°C for several hours. The dried powder was used to study the optical properties of the CdS synthesized nanoparticles. The synthesized nanoparticles were also used to make thin films by using the spin-coating method and scanning electron microscopic study was carried out.

Result and Discussion

Figure 1 shows the optical absorption of CdS nanoparticles. It exhibits strong absorption in the ultraviolet and visible regions, which is characteristic of a direct band-gap of CdS nanoparticles. A pronounced absorption edge is observed in the visible region, indicating the onset of band-to-band electronic transitions from the valence band to the conduction band. For the bulk CdS the absorption edge is near 500-520 nm but for the current CdS nanoparticles, the absorption edge is

blue shifted. This behavior is attributed to quantum confinement effect, which is observed due to reduced particles size. The observed absorption tailing below the band edge is attributed to defects and surface states present in the synthesized nanoparticles. The absorbance spectrum of CdS confirms the successful formation of CdS nanoparticles.

Figure 1: UV-Visible absorption spectrum of synthesized CdS nanoparticles.

Figure 2 shows the surface morphology of CdS nanoparticle thin films prepared via spin-coating technique. The SEM image shows a densely packed thin film composed of CdS nanoparticles. The nanoparticles appear well defined with relatively smooth surfaces and exhibit a narrow size distribution, indicating controlled nucleation and growth during synthesis. The agglomeration of particles is observed in SEM -image. And it is attributed to the solvent used to prepare the CdS nanoparticle solution for spin coating. The clusters of nanoparticles are found in the SEM image reveals the challenge to prepare uniform thin film of CdS nanoparticle. This drawback can be solved using an appropriate solvent to disperse the CdS nanoparticles.

Figure 2: FE-SEM image of CdS nanoparticles prepared by using spin-coating method.

Conclusions

In the present study, CdS nanoparticles were successfully synthesized using chemical precipitation method. The UV-Visible absorbance spectrum showed strong absorption edge in the visible region. The shift the absorption confirms the quantum size effect of synthesized CdS nanoparticles. To realize CdS nanoparticles role in fabrication of opto-electronic devices, we have prepared the CdS nanoparticles films by using spin-coating method. The field-effect Scanning electron microscopic image confirms the nanocrystalline growth of CdS. The synthesized CdS nanoparticle thin films shows the promising features for its potential use in fabrication of optoelectronic devices particularly solar cell, and light-emitting diodes.

Acknowledgement

This paper is dedicated to the Hon. Principal Dr. R. R. Ahire of Vidya Vikas Mandal's Sitaram Govind Patil Arts, Science and Commerce College, Sakri, on the occasion of his superannuation, in respect of his idealistic headship and affection toward research. Authors are greatly thankful to the respective head of the belonging institutes for their constant support and encouragement.

References

1. Pandya, S.; and Raval, K.; Investigation of structural, morphological and optical properties of cadmium sulphide (CdS) thin films at different Cd/S concentration deposited by chemical technique, *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics*, 2017, 28, 18031–18039.
2. Regmi, A.; Basnet, Y.; Bhattarai, S.; Gautam, S. K.; Cadmium Sulfide Nanoparticles: Synthesis, Characterization, and Antimicrobial Study, *Hindawi Journal of Nanomaterials*, 2023, Article ID 8187000, 7.
3. Khatter J. and Chauhan R. P., Effect of temperature on properties of cadmium sulfide nanostructures synthesized by solvothermal method, *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics*. 2020, 31, 2676–2685.
4. Hodes G. Semiconductor and ceramic nanoparticle films deposited by chemical bath deposition. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2007, 9, 2181–2196.
5. Wang, S.; Yu, J.; Zhao, P.; Guo, S.; Han, S. One-Step Synthesis of Water-Soluble CdS Quantum Dots for Silver-Ion Detection. *ACS Omega* 2021, 6, 7139–7146.
6. Bharti, D.B.; Bharati, A.V.; Wankhade, A.V. Synthesis, Characterization and Optical Property Investigation of CdS Nanoparticles, *Luminescence* 2018, 33, 1445–1449.
7. Shalabayev, Z.; Baláž, M.; Khan, N.; Nurlan, Y.; Augustyniak, A.; Daneu, N.; Tatykayev, B.; Dutková, E.; Burashev, G.; Casas-Luna, M.; et al. Sustainable Synthesis of Cadmium Sulfide, with Applicability in Photocatalysis, Hydrogen Production, and as an Antibacterial Agent, Using Two Mechanochemical Protocols. *Nanomaterials* 2022, 12, 1250.
8. Chen, J.; Ma, Q.; Wu, X.-J.; Li, L.; Liu, J.; Zhang, H. Wet-Chemical Synthesis and Applications of Semiconductor Nanomaterial- Based Epitaxial Heterostructures. *Nano-Micro Lett.* 2019, 11, 86.
9. Lopes, P.A.L.; Brandão Santos, M.; Mascarenhas, A.J.S.; Silva, L.A. Synthesis of CdS Nano-Spheres by a Simple and Fast Sonochemical Method at Room Temperature. *Mater. Lett.* 2014, 136, 111–113.

10. Liu, J.; Pu, X.; Zhang, D.; Seo, H.J.; Du, K.; Cai, P. Combustion Synthesis of CdS/Reduced Graphene Oxide Composites and Their Photocatalytic Properties. *Mater. Res. Bull.* 2014, 57, 29–34.
11. Yang, G.; Park, S.J. Conventional and Microwave Hydrothermal Synthesis and Application of Functional Materials: A Review. *Materials* 2019, 12, 1177.
12. Gan, Y.X.; Jayatissa, A.H.; Yu, Z.; Chen, X.; Li, M. Hydrothermal Synthesis of Nanomaterials. *J. Nanomater.* 2020, 2020, e8917013.
13. De La Cruz Terrazas, E.C.; Lazaro, R.A.; Gonzalez, M.M.; Luque, P.A.; Castillo, S.J.; Carrillo-Castillo, A. A simple method for the synthesis of cds nanoparticles using a novel surfactant. *Chalcogenide Lett.* 2015, 12, 147–153.